

NATIVE AND BORROWED TOURISM TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: This article deals with the general overview about native and borrowed words in English and Uzbek languages. The article considers the gradual expanding of vocabulary of each language. As well as, it gives information about the languages themselves, their history and development.

Key words: tourism, tourism terminology, native words, borrowed words(loanwords).

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена общему обзору родных и заимствованных слов в английском и узбекском языках. В статье рассматривается постепенное расширение словарного запаса каждого языка. Кроме того, он дает информацию о самих языках, их истории и развитии.

Ключевые слова: туризм, туристическая терминология, родные слова, заимствованные слова.

Any language in the world mainly consists of two categories of words, they are *native* and *borrowed* ones. Native words are the ones which have existed in the usage of a language since it was appeared and the ones considered to be a member of the original language word stock. For example, *inn*, *homeland* and *sightseeing* are native words in the English language.

Borrowed or loanwords are considered to be the words that have come or have been adopted from another language and modified in accordance with grammatical conventions of the language.

The majority of words in English are borrowed and they constitute more than 70% of total English vocabulary. In addition, Latin and French are one of the primary auxiliary languages for English, meaning that the plenty of tourism terms have also been adopted from Latin and French. Furthermore, one of the reasons why the borrowings occur is that there are no equivalents in English and, especially, they are for objects, social, political or cultural events or abstract concepts. Even though native words are less than borrowed, the former ones constitute almost 80% of the 500 most frequently used words. [6, p 288]

The same concept applies to English tourism terminology. In tourism also there are more borrowed words rather than native ones, it is because tourism does not evolve only in one country, but all over the world, meaning that some terms may not have their equivalents or alternatives in another language. This, in turn, leads to the borrowing of some words. Below some English borrowed words are given:

From Greek:

Catalogue (n) - from Greek katalogos "a list, register, enrollment" (such as the katalogos neon, the "catalogue of ships" in the "Iliad").

Tropic (adj) - from Greek tropikos "of or pertaining to a turn or change; of or pertaining to the solstice" (as a noun, "the solstice," short for tropikos kyklos), from trope "a turning" (from PIE root *trep- "to turn").

From French:

Tourism (n) - 1811, from tour (n.) + -ism. Tour - c. 1300, "a turn, a shift on duty," from Old French tor, tourn, tourn "a turn, trick, round, circuit, circumference," from torner, tourner "to turn".

Hotel (n) - 1640s, "public official residence; large private residence," from French hôtel "a mansion, palace, large house," from Old French ostel, hostel "a lodging" (see hostel). Modern sense of "an inn of the better sort" is first recorded 1765.

Journey (n) - c. 1200, "a defined course of traveling; one's path in life," from Old French journée "a day's length; day's work or travel" (12c.).

Uzbekistan is gradually developing and Uzbek society as well, such improvements, in turn, lead to the further evolvement of the lexicon of Uzbek language. It can be periodized according to the certain stages: 1. The influence of the Persian-Tajik language on the Turkic language until the 15th century; 2. The influence of the Arabic language on the Turkic language in the VIII-X centuries; 3. The influence of the Russian language on the Uzbek language in the XX century; 4. After independence, the influence of various languages on the Uzbek language, in particular English. [8, p. 178 - 194] Vocabulary of Uzbek language has also expanded due to the penetration of neologisms, so that it has somehow influenced the general extending of Uzbek tourism terminology. However, it should be taken into account that despite such developments and enhancements, Uzbek language does not have native tourism terms, but includes large amount of borrowed ones. It also should be said that majority of Uzbek tourism terms were taken from English, Russian, Latin, French and Persian-Tajik. Below some Uzbek borrowed words are given:

From French: *bilet, passport;*

From Farsi-Tajik: *mehmonxona, mezbon;*

From Arabic: *manzil, safar, sayohat;*

From English: *motel, kemping, bar;*

From Russian: *karnaval, vizitka.*

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